

Village fund policy in the time of covid-19 in facing economic impacts and non-militarian threats

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ABSTRACT : Indonesia is one of the countries affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and its spread is still ongoing. The Covid-19 pandemic affects all lines of government both at the center and at the regions. The large flow of funds from the center to the regions, especially village funds, is expected to be optimized for use to deal with Covid-19. The purpose of this study includes the implementation of the village fund policy in dealing with non-military threats (Covid-19). The method used in this research is qualitative with research design using literature study. The research data were taken from journals, books, previous research, scientific articles, literature and news from official websites and the research subject was village funds. The results of the research are that village funds are expected to be optimally utilized and become a driving engine in tackling the impact of COVID-19. The implementation of the village fund policy includes the human resources of the village apparatus, budget resources, village fund bureaucracy and central and regional communication.

KEYWORDS: village funds, covid-19, defense economic, non-military threats

I. INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 has hit the whole world, including Indonesia. This pandemic has an impact not only on the health sector but also on the social, economic and political sectors. Various policies have been issued by the government to minimize the impact of this COVID-19 pandemic. The government in addition to carrying out policies for medical treatment, also makes various policy programs that can help the community directly (Arika Bagus P et al, 2020).

Covid-19 is a non-military threat, especially in the economic field. The Covid-19 pandemic that has occurred since the beginning of 2020 has had a tremendous impact on economic aspects, including the financial condition of existing companies (Henry N.S, Suharnob, Abdul A.A, 2021). Covid-19 has caused economic activity to weaken and be hampered. Many companies terminate employment (PHK) for employees. Employees affected by layoffs come from the formal and non-formal sectors. This caused Indonesia's economic growth to slow down by 2.97% (year on year) which occurred in the first quarter of 2021. When compared to 2020 in the fourth quarter where Indonesia's economic growth could increase to 5.02%. (Livia Fibrianti, 2021).

Various aids were given to the community in various forms such as cash, basic necessities, or cutting electricity tariff bills and so on, which at times like this are certainly needed by many people affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and distributed in the hope that they can meet their daily needs. The main purpose of these assistances is to ensure the availability of basic needs and social protection, especially for vulnerable groups

affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. The vulnerable groups in question are workers who are uncertain in terms of working hours, contracts, scope and guarantees (Arika Bagus P et al, 2020).

Several efforts have been made by the government as a form of prevention and mitigation of the impact of Covid-19, which can be seen with the issuance of Government Regulation in Lieu of Law Number 1 of 2020 concerning State Financial Policy and Financial System Stability for Handling the 2019 Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19) Pandemic and / or In the Context of Facing Threats That Endanger the National Economy and/or Financial System Stability provides a new instrument to minimize the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the village economy. Article 2 paragraph 1 letter (i) of the regulation states that it is necessary to prioritize the use of budget allocations for certain activities (refocusing), adjustment of allocations and or cuts/delays in the distribution of budget transfers to regions and village funds with certain criteria (Tengku Rika Valentina, Roni Ekha Putera and Cici Safitri, 2020).

The Village Fund can be used for activities to handle the COVID-19 pandemic and Village Cash Direct Assistance. Priority for the use of Village Funds includes activities in the context of tackling the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, including activities to handle the COVID-19 pandemic and/or social safety nets in the Village. Based on the Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 3 of 2020 concerning Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) Management in Villages through the Village Budget, the Village Government is required to use the budget for unexpected expenditure activities in the Disaster, Emergency and Urgent Village Management Sector by re-focusing activities and Village Budget for handling COVID-19 (Hefis Kurnia Sandhi and Iskandar, 2020). In terms of communication, it can be seen that the efforts made by the government have not been maximized and it seems that they are not serious about handling the COVID-19 pandemic.(Saputro, 2021).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Utilization of village funds in the context of preventing and handling Covid-19 since 2020 and anticipating impactful solutions is considered to be running with encouraging performance and success. In addition to improving public health and restoring economic growth, the facts on the ground also show the success of the community in creating villages with a clean and healthy environment that has a positive impact on health and productive economic activities (Juli Panglima Saragih, 2021). Defense economics as a multidisciplinary study discusses resource allocation, income distribution, economic growth, and political stability as applied to topics related to defense. According to the defense economy, the impact of the use of the defense budget on the economy can be viewed from the demand or consumption and supply or production approaches (Saputro et al., 2021)

In addition, the government issued regulations that provide flexibility for the transfer of village funds for Covid-19 such as Minister of Finance Regulation No. 40/PMK.07/2020 concerning Amendments to PMK No. 205/PMK.07/2019 concerning Village Fund Management, and Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration No. 6 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Permendes PDTT No. 11 of 2019 which is intended to regulate the priority of using village funds in 2020 for: (1) Prevention and handling of Covid-19; (2) Village Cash Intensive Work; (3) Village Cash Direct Assistance (Tengku Rika Valentina, Roni Ekha Putera and Cici Safitri, 2020). National security system has been built with an approach participation of citizens and society or the security sector reform agreement, the most important thing is how it affects Defense-Security Expenditure Structure againstn security stability in Indonesia (Saputro et al., 2020)

Security Stability and Strategic Industry Growth have a simultaneous effect on Macroeconomic Stability. The integration of the development of security stability together with increasing the growth of strategic industries in a synergistic manner has the ability to increase macroeconomic stability (Saputro & Meirinaldi,

2019). The integration of security stability development together with increasing strategic industrial growth and macroeconomic stability synergistically has the ability to increase economic growth (SAPUTRO, 2021)

Defense budget planning and the right allocation of defense spending every year can support Indonesia's defense forces, so that they are able to create and increase Indonesia's economic growth (Saputro, Rivai, et al., 2021). The obstacles faced in implementing PT Pindad's Anoa combat vehicle production policy in supporting the improvement of the national defense economy were due to limited resources experienced by PT Pindad, namely capital and regulations that support PT Pindad's efforts in export market orientation (mulyani, 2022)

The development of a tourist village is a form of rural development policy that tries to diversify the village which has so far been based on agriculture. Tourism villages are developed to become villages based on the tourism industry, both service businesses and commercial businesses in the form of tourism products (rianto, 2021). The development of a tourism village is a form of rural development policy that tries to diversify villages which have been based mostly on agriculture (prihantoro, 2021)

Strategy for Prevention of Corruption in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI includes Improving the Integrity and Ethics of Operators, Consolidating and Accelerating State Bureaucratic Reforms, Strengthening Anti Corruption Culture in the Community, Firm and Consistent Law Enforcement , and Integrated (Putro, 2021). The defense industry really needs an integrated and structured structure for the long term. It is hoped that the national defense equipment system can be independent to meet domestic needs, that in the long term, our defense equipment can be exported and traded abroad so that it becomes an economic source both from reducing unemployment, state income and being respected by other countries (Hanri, 2021)

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research method, namely the presentation of data in the form of a description of words where the researcher tries to describe the problems that exist from the results of the study. The author uses data collection techniques through non-participant observation methods and documentation, where data is taken from journals, books, previous research, scientific articles, literature and news from official websites.

IV. RESULTS OR DISCUSSION

Policy implementation is an activity that is seen after a valid direction has been issued from a policy which includes efforts to manage inputs to produce outputs or outcomes for the community. In addition, policy implementation is a process to turn policy formulations into policy actions in order to realize the desired final results (Samodra Wibawa, 1994). Global economic conditions are likely to experience a slowdown, the fate of the trade war is not yet clear. With the situation, it is difficult to increase acceptance. As a result, the state budget deficit and debt could increase (saputro, 2021)

The following are aspects that affect the implementation of the village fund policy in dealing with non-military threats (covid-19), namely:

1. Village Apparatus Human Resources

The success or failure of the village administration is highly dependent on the village administration system. Village administration can run smoothly if the quality of humans as human resources can carry out as well as possible, meaning that village administration greatly determines the position of village government. (Nurul Atika, Nurul Umi Ati and Hayat, 2018).

The success of development carried out in the village must of course have strong support from the village government and the community. The village government as a public servant, must have optimal capabilities, and the community must be able to support the programs implemented by the village government. So that the village government and the community must support each other, where the village government is the

driver of participation, the community is also a contributor in the implementation of village development, where both support and complement each other in every development activity in the village (Muhammad Nawawi, 2018).

The success of the village government is marked by the success of village government administrators including village government officials in carrying out their responsibilities, whose essence is the implementation of service functions. One of the highlights that hinders the performance of public services in rural areas is due to the lack of understanding and awareness of village government officials towards the service sector, including the low quality of the apparatus so that it affects the maximum service system (Muhammad Nawawi, 2018).

The quality of human resources managing the Village Fund is not evenly distributed between villages. Submission of Village Funds requires documents that must be made and signed by the Village Head. These documents are mostly the output of applications to facilitate data entry and Village Fund reporting. Thus, village officials must understand technology and have supporting infrastructure for Information and Communication Technology (ICT). In addition, policies related to the Village Fund are dynamic in adapting to current conditions. Changes in regulations must be addressed and acted upon quickly so as not to hinder the process of distributing Village Funds. In this case, the government continues to strive to improve the synchronization and harmonization of Village Fund policies through improving the provision of quality databases and monitoring and evaluation of Village Funds (Muhammad Nawawi, 2018).

2. Budget Resources

The central government has allocated a village fund budget of IDR 400.1 trillion from 2015 to 2021. An increase in the allocation of village funds of IDR 400.1 trillion over the next 6 years is possible because the village budget continues to increase every year. The total village fund budget of IDR 400.1 trillion since 2015 has never decreased every year. The details are Rp 20.67 trillion (2015), Rp 46.98 trillion (2016), Rp 60 trillion (2017), Rp 60 trillion (2018), and Rp 70 trillion (2019), Rp 72 trillion (2020) (nr/rsa, 2019). The village fund is given to all villages in Indonesia with a formula of 77 percent divided equally among all villages. Then 20 percent is allocated for additional proportions to villages based on population, poverty level, level of geographical difficulty and area. Then, three percent is allocated for additional villages with lagging status. (Sandro Gatra, 2019)

The legal basis for using the Village Fund is regulated based on the Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 3 of 2020 concerning Covid-19 Handling through APBDes, Mendes PDTT Instruction No. 1 of 2021 concerning the Use of Village Funds in 2021 in the Implementation of Micro-Scale PPKM in Villages, Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 13 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Micro-Based PPKM and Optimizing the Covid-19 Handling Command Post at the Village and Sub-District Levels, as well as the Minister of Home Affairs Circular No. 143/575/SJ concerning the Acceleration and Implementation of Village Funds in 2021 (Hasan, 2021).

Based on the Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 3 of 2020 regarding Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) Management in Villages through the Village Budget, the Village Government is required to use the budget for unexpected expenditure activities in the Disaster, Emergency and Urgent Village Management Sector by re-focusing activities and APBD Villages for handling COVID-19 (Hefis Kurnia Sandhi and Iskandar, 2020).

3. Village Fund Bureaucracy

Village funds are defined as funds sourced from the APBN which are intended for Villages which are transferred through the Regency/City APBD and are used to finance government administration, development implementation, development, community development and community empowerment (Village Law Number 6 of 2014).

Based on Government Regulation Number 60 of 2014 concerning Village Funds sourced from the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN), the mechanism for distributing Village Funds is divided into 2 (two) stages, namely the stage of the APBN transfer mechanism from the State General Treasury Account

(RKUN) to the Cash Account. Regional General Affairs (RKUD) and the stage of the APBD transfer mechanism from the RKUD to the village treasury.

The calculation and determination of the Village Fund ceiling per village by the Government is expected to accelerate the process of direct distribution from the RKUN to the RKDes. So far, the calculation and determination of the Village Fund is carried out by the Regional Government (Pemda) and is officially stipulated in a Regional Head Regulation (Perkada). The process of determining this Perkada takes a long time, resulting in the distribution of Village Funds being hampered because there is no legal basis for it. With the direct determination of the Village Fund by the Government, the Regional Government can immediately apply for distribution at the beginning of the fiscal year through the State Treasury Service Office (KPPN). The direct distribution of Village Funds from the RKUN to the RKDes is intended so that villages can directly utilize the Village Funds they receive in accordance with the work program that has been set (Tatag Prihantara Yuwono, 2022).

Several types of assistance from the government during the Covid-19 pandemic for the community through village funds:

a. Direct Village Fund Cash Assistance (BLT-Village Fund)

In the Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration No. 6 of 2020 article 1 number 28 concerning amendments to the Village Minister Regulation, PDTT Number 11 of 2019 concerning the Priority for the Use of Village Funds in 2020, it is explained about the Direct Village Fund Cash Assistance, which is abbreviated as BLT-Dana Desa, is the provision of cash to families who cannot afford or poor in villages to ease the economic burden as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. Villages have social and economic resources and can contribute to handling Covid-19, especially in the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBDes) and Village Funds. The Village Fund is an On Budget budget allocation that can be used directly to reduce the disaster impact of Covid-19 at the household level and Villages (Priadi Asmanto et al, 2020).

b. Cash Social Assistance (BST)

Unlike the case with the BLT-Village Fund which is regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia No. 6 of 2020, there are no statutory regulations that regulate in detail related to BST. The rules related to BST are only contained in the Decree of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 54/HUK/2020 concerning the Implementation of Basic Food Social Assistance and Cash Social Assistance in Handling the Impact of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19). It stipulates that the data on families receiving cash social assistance will be prioritized from integrated social welfare data and can come from recommendations from district/city governments. The requirements for BST recipients are people who are included in the RT/RW data collection, have lost their livelihoods during the Covid-19 pandemic, which not registered in other social assistance programs such as PKH, BPNT, Basic Food Cards and Pre-Employment Cards (Nunik Dewi Pramanik, 2020).

4. Communication Regions and Center

In carrying out the authority between the Central Government and the Regional Government there needs to be harmonious communication and so that the program runs smoothly. The relationship of authority between the Central Government and the Regional Government must be regulated in laws and regulations, so that the relationship has legitimacy and mutual regulation. The existence of the principle of decentralization is a form of authority relationship between the Central Government and Regional Governments. One form of the relationship between the authority of the Central Government and the Regional Government is the Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. Law 23 of 2014 regulates the division of tasks between the Central Government and Regional Governments (Abdul Rauf Alauddin Said, 2015).

In addition, the relationship of authority between the Central Government and the Regional Government is a form of delegation of authority from the Central Government to the Regional Government, where although Law 23 of 2014 regulates the authority of the Regional Government, this authority is a delegation from the Central Government to the Regional Government. Law Number 23 of 2014 has regulated the division of Government affairs, whether it is Absolute, Concurrent and General. Based on Article 10 concerning absolute government affairs, absolute government affairs are carried out by the Central Government directly which consists of Foreign Policy, Defense, Security, Justice, Monetary and national fiscal and Religion (Wirazilmustan, Rahmat, 2018).

In order to establish a harmonious relationship between the Central Government and the Regional Government in carrying out their authority, between the Central Government and the Regional Government there must be a good communication relationship between the Central Government and the Regional Government. Communication is a very important dimension for government organizations. Mainstream government communication to make a policy to run smoothly and as a flow of public information (Ulber Silalahi, 2004). The pattern of relations between the Central Government and Regional Governments, namely the control of the Central Government by the delegation of affairs through the preparation of norms, standard procedures and criteria prepared by the Central Government as the basis for the Regional Government to carry out the affairs given by the Central Government to the Regional Government, the existence of guidance and supervision of the administration of government affairs between the Ministry and the Regional Government and the President. This pattern relationship can run smoothly with good communication between the Central Government and Local Government (Septi Nur Wijayanti, 2016).

Thus, Indonesia should have good crisis communication skills in response to disasters and crises that can occur at any time, and can also reduce the impact of the current Covid-19 (Dhika Rizky, 2022). The central government and local governments, especially villages, need to be in line with the programs that have been set so that their impact is more optimal. Strengthening focus and priorities for the use of Village Funds in order to support the National Economic Recovery (PEN) program due to the Covid-19 pandemic. In the midst of the current pandemic situation, the Village Fund is used for social protection programs in the form of Village BLT with a target of 8 million Beneficiary Families (KPM). The Village Fund is also used to support food and animal security programs and to improve public health, including reducing stunting and handling Covid-19 in villages. In addition, the Village Fund is used for village infrastructure development programs by prioritizing the use of local labor and raw materials, and village development programs in accordance with the potential and characteristics of the village. Thus, the use of the Village Fund is expected to be balanced between the handling of Covid-19 and infrastructure development in the village (Tatag Prihantara Yuwono, 2022).

V. CONCLUSION

The government has issued various policies to minimize the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The government in addition to issuing policies for the health sector, but also makes various policy programs that can help the community directly. The Village Fund can be used for activities to handle the COVID-19 pandemic and Village Cash Direct Assistance. Priority for the use of Village Funds includes activities in order to overcome the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The implementation of village fund policies includes human resources for village apparatus, budget resources, village fund bureaucracy and central and regional communications.

Suggestion:

According to the 2015-2020 Village Fund Brief Review published by the Center for Budget Studies, the Secretariat General of the DPR RI, the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration (KemendesPDRT) need to strengthen coordination and synergy with the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Home Affairs, Central Statistics Agency, Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP), and Local Government (Robby Alexander Sirait and Emillia Octavia, 2021). Coordination and synergy in the form of:

- a. Improvement of the village fund allocation database so that it is appropriate, equal, adequate

and reliable (especially the number of poor people and the size of the area). This is necessary so that the allocation of village funds can be carried out appropriately and appropriately.

b. Synchronization of the determination of good beneficiary villages proposed by the regional government with those determined by the ministry of finance. This is so that the difference in determination between the proposed one and the one set by the Ministry of Finance does not repeat itself in the future.

c. Reduce the potential for differences in the value of the allocation per village between those stipulated in the bupati/mayor regulations and the calculations made by the Ministry of Finance.

d. Monitoring and determining the time limit for the distribution of the remaining Village Funds in the Regional General Treasury Account (RKUD) and Village Cash Account (RKD).

e. Strengthening the role of the ineffective Professional Assistance Team (TPP) in increasing the capacity, effectiveness, and accountability of village government and village development.

f. Strengthening the guidance and supervision of local governments with BPKP in terms of managing village funds so that they are able to reduce the misuse of village funds by village officials and be able to increase the accuracy of the use of village funds in accordance with the purpose of allocating village funds through the APBN as mandated by the Village Law.

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